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Ostbayerische Technische Hochschule Amberg-Weiden
Department of Electrical Engineering, Media and Computer
Science

Applied Research in Engineering Sciences

Master Thesis

by

Ruben Prokscha

**Realization of a Service Pipeline for Traffic Density
Estimation and Prediction based on Traffic Data using
Machine Learning**

Realisierung einer Servicepipeline zur Schätzung und
Vorhersage der Verkehrsdichte auf Basis von Verkehrsdaten
unter Verwendung von maschinellem Lernen

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Editing Period: from 21th June 2021
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I hereby declare that the Master Thesis with the title:

**Realization of a Service Pipeline for Traffic Density Estimation and Prediction
based on Traffic Data using Machine Learning**

is my own unaided work and was not filled for other exams. I also declare, that I have
only used sources which are listed in the bibliography.

Date: **January 17, 2022**

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Master Thesis Summary

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**Realization of a Service Pipeline for Traffic Density Estimation and Prediction
based on Traffic Data using Machine Learning**

Abstract:

The progressive development of microelectronics enables more and more computing power in a smaller form factor. In the embedded sector, where low power consumption is an additional requirement, this progress is particularly significant. Economical, compact yet powerful platforms can be integrated into infrastructure elements to transform them into stand-alone computing nodes (edge devices). This results in the advantage of decentralized data processing with low latency. Such smart nodes can communicate with each other in the form of fog computing and share workloads among themselves. For *Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS)*, such a development could enable traffic orchestration in a smart city context. Due to the outstanding opportunities such a paradigm shift in data processing insinuates, a closer look at the current state of the art is in order. A key goal is to characterize novel edge hardware by generating key performance indicators. Furthermore, it is demonstrated how embedded *Artificial Intelligence (AI)* can be put into effect for future *Mobility as a Service (MaaS)* applications.

Keywords: Edge, Machine Learning, Service Pipeline

Contents

Acronyms	vii
1 Introduction	1
2 Hardware Setup	3
2.1 NVIDIA Jetson Platforms	3
2.2 Intel Neural Compute Stick 2	5
2.3 Google Coral Edge TPU	5
2.4 FLIR Flea3 USB Camera	6
2.5 Energy Monitoring System	6
2.6 Table Assembly	7
3 Object Detection	9
3.1 Methodology	9
3.2 You Only Look Once	11
3.3 Result Preparation and Evaluation	12
3.4 Traffic Datasets	14
3.4.1 Microsoft COCO	15
3.4.2 Cityscape	16
3.4.3 KITTI	16
3.4.4 Citycam	17
3.4.5 Tampere	17
3.5 Transfer Learning	19
4 Microservices	21
4.1 Advantages and Critique	22
4.2 Inter Service Communication	23
4.3 Software Stack	24
4.4 Inference Service	25
4.4.1 Architecture	26
4.5 Edge Benchmark Service	27
4.5.1 Related Work	28
4.5.2 Architecture	28
5 Pipeline Evaluation	31

5.1	Performance Characterization	31
5.1.1	Timing Evaluation	32
5.1.2	Energy and Power Demand	33
5.2	Transfer Learning Detection Accuracy	37
5.3	Traffic Density Estimation and Prediction	40
5.3.1	Related Work	41
5.3.2	Evaluation	41
5.3.3	Forecasting Model	45
5.3.4	Future Improvements	47
5.4	Road Side Unit Realization	48
6	Summary and Future Work	51
	Bibliography	53
	List of Figures	60
	List of Tables	61
	List of Listings	62
	Appendix	64

Acronyms

ACF	Autocorrelation Function
ADF	augmented Dickey Fuller test
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI4DI	Artificial Intelligence for Digitizing Industry
AIoT	Artificial Intelligence of Things
AP	Average Precision
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Auto Regressive
ARM	Advanced RISC Machines
AUC	Area Under the Curve
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
CNN	Convolutional Neural Networks
COCO	Common Objects in Context
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRC	Cyclic Redundancy Check
CRUD	Create Read Update Delete
CUDA	Compute Unified Device Architecture
cuDNN	CUDA Deep Neural Network Library
CV	Computer Vision
DK	Development Kit
DL	Deep Learning

ECS	Electronic Components and Systems
EMS	Energy Monitoring System
FN	False Negative
FP	False Positive
FPS	Frames Per Second
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GRU	Gated Recurrent Unit
HD	High Definition
HPC	High Performance Computing
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IoT	Internet of Things
IoU	Intersection over Union
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
JPEG	Joint Photographic Experts Group
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KDE	Kernel Density Estimation
KITTI	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology and Toyota Technological Institute
LoRaWAN	Long Range Wide Area Network
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MA	Moving Average
MaaS	Mobility as a Service
MAC	Multiply Accumulate
MAC	Media Access Control
mAP	mean Average Precision
MCU	Microcontroller Unit

ML	Machine Learning
MSE	Mean Squared Error
NCS2	Neural Compute Stick 2
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NMS	Non Maximum Suppression
NPU	Neural Processing Unit
ONNX	Open Neural Network Exchange
OpenCL	Open Computing Language
OpenCV	Open Computer Vision
OpenVINO	Open Visual Inference and Neural network Optimization
OPS	Operations Per Second
P	Precision
PACF	Partial Autocorrelation Function
PCIe	Peripheral Component Interconnect Express
PnP	Plug and Play
R	Recall
R-CNN	Region Based Convolutional Neural Networks
RAM	Random Access Memory
REST	Representational State Transfer
RISC	Reduced Instruction Set Computer
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
RPC	Remote Procedure Call
RPN	Region Proposal Network
RSU	Road Side Unit
SaaS	Software as a Service
Shave	Streaming Hybrid Architecture Vector Engine

SOA	Service Oriented Architecture
SoC	System on a Chip
SORT	Simple Online and Realtime Tracking
SOTA	state-of-the-art
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
SSD	Single Shot Detector
TF	Tensorflow
TN	True Negative
TP	True Positive
TPU	Tensor Processing Unit
TRT	TensorRT
UART	Universal Asynchronous Receiver Transmitter
UI	User Interface
USB	Universal Serial Bus
UUT	Unit Under Test
VPU	Vision Processing Unit
YOLO	You Only Look Once

Chapter 1

Introduction

In recent years, two major advances in technology started a shift in conventional data processing. For once, *AI* is maturing from a mere research topic to an ubiquitous extension of our day to day life. Self driving cars, robots and digital assistance are more and more tangible with each new groundbreaking publication. Such a transition is induced by major improvements of the underlying algorithms as well as streamlined accessibility brought forth by high level frameworks with comprehensive documentation. The other subject is a transformation of overall passive systems to be progressively enriched by active computing elements. Modern cars are featuring infotainment systems offering navigation, driving assistant and mobile communication. The same alteration holds equally true for household appliances (smart home) and industrial applications. Such smart devices generate ample information in form of sensor data and event records. Generally, such intelligence is either externally evaluated, conditionally analyzed (fault detection) or discarded entirely. The next logical step is the unification of both embedded devices and *Artificial Intelligence*. Such edge computing would entail data acquisition, preparation and *AI* driven processing at the source. Hence, data is refined on site and just the findings are transmitted to a remote location for further evaluation.

This paradigm shift and its potential consequences have attracted the attention of the European Union. The three associations AENEAS, ARTEMIS-IA and EPOSS participated in compiling a *Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)* [1] with the intention of addressing upcoming challenges in the field of *Electronic Components and Systems (ECS)* for intereuropean collaborations. Edge computing is a major concern of this document. However, realizing such an ambitious endeavor requires a fundamental rethinking of the underlying software architectures. Smart devices must be able to independently interact with each other to manage a variety of pliable workloads. A possible concept to provide such flexibility is the deployment of platform independent micro services. Several of these building blocks could be chained together to form customizable data pipelines.

The *SRIA* elaborates a variety of benefits gained from such an undertaking. Most prominent is the reduction of energy demand brought forth by a decrease in data

transfer, superseding decentralized cloud computing [2] and utilizing highly efficient *Reduced Instruction Set Computer (RISC)* architectures. The local evaluation of raw sensor data presents further upside in terms of privacy [3]. Potentially sensitive imagery such as camera data must ensure anonymization before transmission to avoid privacy breaches. This step could be omitted by preconnecting embedded intelligence for data synthetization. A neural network conveniently operates as an anonymizer by only extracting relevant information from an input and neglecting possibly sensitive data. In terms of automation a great potential can arise from decentralized computing. While single platform is limited in its realm of operation, several edge devices could resolve more complex workloads by interacting with each other. Such heterogeneous edge clusters have the potential to develop a fundamental 'understanding' of an environment and therefore independently initiate actions to circumvent undesirable outcomes. A breakthrough of this scale would enable fully automated driving and trigger the development of novel technologies. A vivid demonstration of the possibilities opened by decentralized edge swarms can be found in [4].

This work addresses the issue of moving *Machine Learning (ML)* from cloud servers to an edge environment. An exemplary *Microservice* pipeline was designed that demonstrates embedded processing of traffic data in the field. The area of *Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS)* presents a wide range of vivid optimization potential, which is crucial not least for achieving climate goals. The pipeline analyzes traffic camera data using AI algorithms for object recognition. The results are further processed for generating real-time traffic density estimates and forecasts. The methodology and architecture presented in this research are independent of the field of application and are therefore viewed separately. Chapter 2 contributes an overview of *state-of-the-art (SOTA)* edge solutions which are targeted for embedded intelligence. Such devices offer novel *AI* accelerators which are also within the scope of the *ECS-SRIA*. These platforms are part of the base setup for subsequent implementations. In the following chapter, the subject of object detection is explained to outline the core component of the data pipeline. Chapter 4 gives further insight on the subject of *Microservices* and the conceptualization of *Artificial Intelligence (AI)* deployments. In Chapter 5 several data pipelines are assembled to evaluate both energy consumption and performance of an edge platform running a *SOTA* object detection algorithm. This is meant to provide an indication of what is achievable in terms of edge computing. Furthermore, the benefits of transfer learning are evaluated and a demonstration for traffic density estimation and forecasting is shown for a smart city context. Last but not least, a synopsis is given to assess existing solutions in terms of performance and feasibility.

Chapter 2

Hardware Setup

Modern *AI* algorithms differ significantly from common computational tasks. Most *Deep Learning (DL)* models rely heavily on convolutions or dense operations. On the hardware side, this requires large amounts of vector *Multiply Accumulate (MAC)* instructions to be processed. General purpose *CPUs* are not designed to meet the demands of such a workload. It is therefore inevitable that new hardware appeared on the market to address this exact issue. The following chapter gives an oversight of three types of coprocessors which enable highly efficient *Deep Learning* calculations (inferences) in energy restricted edge environment.

2.1 NVIDIA Jetson Platforms

Graphic cards are designed to handle large amounts of linear algebra calculations in parallel. Hence, they are commonly used for *ML* tasks and scientific calculations in server farms. NVIDIA's approach for addressing edge inference is coupling an *ARM CPU* with an embedded version of their *Graphics Processing Units (GPUs)*. The Jetson Family (Figure 2.1) enables *GPU* computation in an independent low power environment. Table 2.1 provides a brief comparison of the three platforms.

(a) NVIDIA Jetson Nano. (b) NVIDIA Jetson TX2 DK. (c) NVIDIA Jetson Xavier.

Figure 2.1: NVIDIA inference accelerator platforms.

Each platform can be operated in different power modes to balance energy consumption and performance. The Jetson Nano (Figure 2.1a) represents the lower end on the performance scale. It can operate at 10 W down to 5 W for reduced energy consumption

to enable battery driven *AI* applications. The built in Maxwell *GPU* is not ideal for modern *AI* purposes due to its age. Only single and double precision operations are calculated directly by the devices *Compute Unified Device Architecture (CUDA)* cores. The amount of 4 GB *RAM* presents an additional limitation for the area of operation.

The Jetson TX2 platform (Figure 2.1b) operates in the range of 5 W to 15 W, depending on the chosen power mode. It uses the same *ARM* quad core *CPU* as the Nano with two additional NVIDIA Denver cores. It has 8 GB memory and a more recent *GPU* which supports half precision data types.

Figure 2.1c depicts the Jetson AGX Xavier. It is the most powerful of the three platforms and can be utilized for more demanding applications. Hence, 32 GB *RAM* and an eight core NVIDIA Carmel *CPU* are provided by the device. The Volta *GPU* introduced specialized tensor cores, which are able to drastically accelerate 16 bit floating point operations. Additionally, quantized 8 bit integer operations are supported by the devices *CUDA* cores. The power demand can be adjusted between 10 W, 15 W and 30 W.

In November 2021, NVIDIA introduced their upcoming top model for edge inference, the Jetson AGX Orin [5]. It will be based on an NVIDIA Ampere *GPU*, which will enable different kinds of data types to be accelerated by tensor cores. Hence, mixed precision *AI* tasks can be efficiently processed by edge nodes in the near future.

Utilizing *GPU* acceleration of such devices requires the use of low level libraries. NVIDIA provides its proprietary *CUDA* framework and the *CUDA Deep Neural Network Library (cuDNN)* for this very purpose. Additionally, NVIDIA TensorRT can be utilized to perform hardware specific low level optimizations to further increase performance. As an alternative to the NVIDIA framework, the *Open Computing Language (OpenCL)* could also be used for *GPU* calculations. However, most high level frameworks are not (fully) supporting such an approach. This is not least due to the lower performance compared to *CUDA* [6].

	Jetson Nano	Jetson TX2 DK	Jetson AGX Xavier
CPU	Quad-Core ARM Cortex A57	Dual-Core NVIDIA Denver 1.5 Quad-Core ARM Cortex A57	Octa-Core NVIDIA Carmel
RAM	4 GB LPDDR4	8 GB LPDDR4	32 GB LPDDR4x
GPU Architecture	Maxwell (2014)	Pascal (2016)	Volta (2017)
GPU Units	128 CUDA Cores	256 CUDA Cores	512 CUDA Cores 64 Tensor Cores
Tensor Core Precisions	-	-	FP16
CUDA Core Precisions	FP64, FP32	FP64, FP32, FP16	FP64, FP32, FP16, INT8

Table 2.1: NVIDIA Jetson hardware specifications [7].

2.2 Intel Neural Compute Stick 2

Instead of relying on conventional *GPUs*, Intel designed a specialized *Vision Processing Unit (VPU)* to meet the challenge of edge computing. As the name suggests, the main focus of such a device is the execution of computer vision tasks such as image classification and object detection. Figure 2.2 depicts the Intel *Neural Compute Stick 2 (NCS2)* alongside an Raspberry Pi4.

Figure 2.2: Raspberry Pi 4 with an Intel Neural Compute Stick 2.

The *USB 3.1* device contains the Intel Movidius Myriad X *VPU*. In this configuration it can be used as *Plug and Play (PnP)* coprocessor with an arbitrary platform. The core consists of 16 128 bit *Streaming Hybrid Architecture Vector Engine (Shave)* units with 4 GB *RAM* [8]. It has a nominal power demand between 1 W and 2 W.

The low level communication with the device is handled by the *Open Visual Inference and Neural network Optimization (OpenVINO)* toolkit. The software can also be utilized to run and optimize *AI* tasks for Intel *CPUs* and *GPUs*. *OpenVINO* can be integrated into other applications due to the open source nature of the software.

2.3 Google Coral Edge TPU

Similar to Intels *VPU* approach, Google developed their own hardware for edge inference. This specialized *Tensor Processing Unit (TPU)* can be added to existing systems via a *USB*, *mPCIe* or *M.2* interface. Approximately 8 MB *RAM* are provided per unit and the peak power consumption is rated at 2 W. Additionally, multiple of these coprocessors can be chained together to handle a bigger workload. Figure 2.3 depicts the Coral Development Board and a Coral *USB Accelerator* dongle. The board couples an edge *TPU* with an *ARM* quad core *CPU* and 1 GB or 4 GB *RAM*[9].

Figure 2.3: Google Coral Dev Board and Coral USB Accelerator.

The *TPU* hardware is only able to work with 8 Bit integer variables. This benefits both the performance and power consumption, due to reduced complexity in the hardware

design. However, weight quantization must be enforced to use the hardware for common *AI* tasks. This reduction in precision from usually 32 Bit floating point variables to 8 Bit integers inevitably introduces a loss in accuracy. Additionally, quantization and dequantization operations are added to the execution graph, which cause further overhead.

A special pipeline is required to make use of the coprocessor. An algorithm has to be implemented in or ported to the *Tensorflow* (*TF*) framework. There, a *TFLite* converter is used for both quantization and conversion to a *TFLite* FlatBuffer [10] format. A proprietary edge *TPU* compiler is required to translate the *TFLite* instructions for the edge *TPU*. The *TFLite* runtime (a subset of the *Tensorflow* package) is further used to execute the created file. The low level communication is handled by the 'libedgetpu1' library.

Due to this rather convoluted pipeline and the closed source compiler, it is not possible to use the edge *TPU* with other high level frameworks. Additionally, the coprocessor only supports a reduced instruction set. This can result in a scenario, where only a small portion of the algorithm is actually executed on the device itself, while most instructions fall back to *CPU* execution. In some cases, the *TFLite* will not compile at all, which is problematic to debug due to the proprietary compiler design.

2.4 FLIR Flea3 USB Camera

The FLIR Flea3 FL3-U3-32S2C-CS *USB3* camera in Figure 2.4 provides a source for real time *High Definition* (*HD*) image data. It can capture 60 RGB images per seconds at a resolution of 2080x1552 pixels. An additional Computar A4Z2812CS-MPIR lens is mounted with a focal length of 2.8 mm up to 10 mm.

Figure 2.4: FLIR Flea3 USB3 camera with Computar CS mount lens.

The data acquisition is handled by the low level *dc1394* library. It can be used alongside *GStreamer* or *Open Computer Vision* (*OpenCV*) to form a post processing pipeline. This way demosaicing [11], denoising and other algorithms can be performed in succession.

2.5 Energy Monitoring System

The power consumption is a critical metric for edge computing. Especially battery driven environments require a low energy footprint. It is important to allow for a sensible comparison of the different devices in this regard. To obtain this data, an

Energy Monitoring System (EMS) prototype (Figure 2.5) was designed to measure supply voltage and current readings from various heterogeneous devices [12].

Figure 2.5: Energy Monitoring System v1 with extension modules.

A modular construction enables flexible selection between different connectors. Each module utilizes an INA220 sensor to allow the measurement of up to four devices. Each extension card can be operated with a different voltage level from an individual power supply. Therefore, *USB* powered devices can be monitored simultaneously alongside platforms which require a 19 V input voltage.

The motherboard of the *EMS* is powered by a *STM32H750 Microcontroller Unit (MCU)*. It offers various interfaces for communication. At the moment, *UART* and *LoRaWAN* are supported for data transfer. A compact, one channel energy monitor is considered for future development. This will enable decentralized, uninterrupted measurements. That can be especially useful for measuring real time *ITS* application remotely.

The monitor samples the whole sensor array with up to 50 Hz. Each measurement cycle is annotated with an additional time stamp and a *Cyclic Redundancy Check (CRC)* checksum to ensure data integrity.

2.6 Table Assembly

Figure 2.6 depicts how the previously introduced devices are assembled in a demonstrator setup. All platforms are connected via Ethernet to allow for fast uninterrupted measurements. *TPUs* and *VPUs* were added to the platforms to allow for a wide range of test scenarios.

All devices are powered by the *EMS*. A Raspberry Pi 3B is used as endpoint to request energy measurements. It is configured to refine the raw *EMS* data into a more readable format. A simple start, stop, download mechanism was chosen to obtain the device power consumption for a selected time frame.

Figure 2.6: Hardware setup with various edge platforms and accelerators.

Chapter 3

Object Detection

Realizing autonomous systems like self driving cars requires the underlying hardware to have some sort of 'understanding' about the world it is interacting with. The field of *Computer Vision (CV)* is concerned with creating an as accurate as possible model of the environment by evaluating visual sensor data. A subdomain of CV is the topic of object detection. The key objective of this discipline is to determine the spacial location of objects of interest inside image data. Figure 3.1 shows the visualized result of such a detection algorithm on a traffic camera frame. Each object is characterized by its bounding box, label and detection uncertainty.

Figure 3.1: Object detection performed on a traffic camera frame from Tampere City (Finland) [13].

3.1 Methodology

Developing an object detection algorithm is a challenging task. The two major aspects which need to be considered are the detection and the classification of objects located within in the space of an input image.

By limiting the object count per image to one, only a classification problem remains to be solved. For such challenges *Convolutional Neural Networkss (CNNs)* became the

universal solution. Since LeNet [14] was introduced in 1989, many improvements were made. Modern *CNNs* like EfficientNet [15] enable highly accurate classification and can be scaled to optimize model size and computational effort for a specific task.

A naive approach for object detection is the utilization of such an established *CNN* for image classification (ref. Figure 3.2). The network processes the input of a sliding window to detect possible objects within the frame. Confidence values for each window are used to determine the position and class of the contained objects. This procedure could work in theory, however the computational effort would be disproportionately high and therefore the inference time particularly slow.

Figure 3.2: Using an image classifier as object detector by using a sliding window as input.

A more promising concept is the usage of a region proposal algorithm such as selective search [16]. Figure 3.3 shows how only the proposed regions of interest are processed by the classifier. This in turn reduces the number of calculations required to process an image. *Region Based Convolutional Neural Networks (R-CNN)* [17] incorporate this so called two stage network design. Further improvements were made by *Fast-R-CNN* [18], using a *CNN* network as backbone to create a compact feature map of the image to detect objects. *Faster-R-CNN* [19] introduced an even more significant speedup by replacing the region proposal algorithm with a trainable *Region Proposal Network (RPN)*.

Figure 3.3: Using region proposals with an image classifier to detect objects.

While *Faster-RCNN* surpasses its predecessors in speed and accuracy, it is still too large and slow for real time application on embedded devices. Here, one stage detectors come into play. Instead of calculating the region proposals and classifications one after another, both are determined simultaneously. Similar to modern two stage detectors, a backbone *CNN* network is used to generate a feature map of the input image which is further processed by the models neck and head to determine object boxes and classes.

Figure 3.4 depicts how the feature map is divided into a grid pattern. For each grid cell, anchor boxes of different aspect ratios are applied. The subsequent part of the network is responsible for calculating label and objectiveness scores as well as offset parameters for the anchor boxes. To detect objects of various sizes, the feature map can be analyzed at different scales.

Figure 3.4: One stage detector: Illustration with 5x5 grid and three anchor boxes.

3.2 You Only Look Once

The *You Only Look Once (YOLO)* architecture [20] is among the most prominent surrogates of one stage object detectors. Contrary to *Single Shot Detectors (SSDs)* [21] which utilize well established *CNNs* as backbone (e.g. *SSD-MobileNet* [22] or *SSD-ResNet* [23]), *YOLO* employs their own Darknet architecture [24].

Since the release of the first version, *YOLO* has been incrementally improved in terms of accuracy and speed. *YOLOv2 (YOLO9000)* [25] introduced anchor boxes (ref. Figure 3.4), Batch Normalization [26] and higher input resolution. The third version [27] increased the number of backbone layers from 19 to 53 and analysed the input features in three different resolutions to detect objects of varying sizes. Notable, the original *YOLO* developer Joseph Redmon retired from his work on *Computer Vision* after the paper release due to moral implications of his work. *YOLOv4* [28] offered various micro optimizations of the model design and made use of data augmentation during the training process to increase detection robustness. With Scaled-*YOLOv4* model scaling was introduced. Similar to Google's EfficientDet [29] a network can easily be scaled in width and depth to individually optimize model size, accuracy and performance for a certain task. *YOLOv5* [30] is in constant development by Ultralytics.

It is not part of the original *YOLO* project and a peer reviewed paper, describing the model architecture and novel techniques, is still pending. Ultralytics founder and CEO Glenn Jocher, targeted a release for December 1st, 2021 which was not met for untold reasons [31]. Regardless, a notable improvement is the implementation of adaptive anchor boxes [32] which are self adjusting to comply with objects from new datasets. The model accuracy can compete and even surpass other *state-of-the-art* object detectors. Pretrained models of different sizes (n, s, m, l, x) are available with input sizes of 640 px*640 px and 1280 px*1280 px. A user friendly framework makes transfer learning and model export more accessible than previous *YOLO* iterations.

3.3 Result Preparation and Evaluation

Object detectors usually produce several possible bounding boxes for each detection. *YOLOv5* for example calculates a fixed amount of 25200 boxes for every input image. This number comes about by adding up the outputs of the three heads with an grid size of respectively 20^2 , 40^2 and 80^2 detections. Each detection is represented as a vector consisting of box offsets, objectiveness score and class probabilities. Hence, a network, which is trained on 80 different classes produces 25200 possible detection vectors with a length of 85 (ref. Figure 3.5).

box_x	box_y	box_w	box_h	obj.	p(0)	p(1)	...	p(79)
-------	-------	-------	-------	------	------	------	-----	-------

Figure 3.5: YOLOv5 output format for one detection.

Most detections can be discarded by utilizing a confidence threshold. This is done by multiplying the objectiveness score with each class score and comparing the maximum with a predefined threshold value. Figure 3.6 visualizes the effect of thresholding. In Figure 3.6a the whole image is covered with boxes of low probability, while Figure 3.6b shows how even a small confidence threshold of 0.1 can reduce the number of candidates significantly.

(a) Confidence threshold: 0.0

(b) Confidence threshold: 0.1

Figure 3.6: YOLOv5 image inference before (a) and after (b) thresholding.

Nonetheless several boxes per object remain. To further reduce the detections, a technique is required to find the most fitting box for each object. One such approach is

called *Non Maximum Suppression (NMS)*. This iterative algorithm analyses how much the box with the highest confidence overlaps with the other boxes. Figure 3.7 illustrates how such a metric called *Intersection over Union (IoU)* is defined. The overlapping area of two boxes is normalized by dividing it with the area of union. This guarantees a value between zero and one, where zero represents two disjunct areas and one is synonymous with perfect congruence. *NMS* applies a threshold that is used to determine which boxes are being discarded. Here, the detections with a high *IoU* are suppressed to be left with the most promising candidate. Usually, *NMS* is applied for each class separately. However, if an object has traits of two classes, for example a pickup truck (car and truck), it could be useful to use cross class *NMS* to avoid double detections.

$$\text{IoU} = \frac{\text{Overlap}}{\text{Union}}$$

The diagram shows the formula $\text{IoU} = \frac{\text{Overlap}}{\text{Union}}$. On the left, the word 'IoU' is followed by an equals sign. To the right of the equals sign is a small image of a car with two overlapping red bounding boxes. Below this image is the word 'Overlap'. To the right of this is a division symbol (\div). To the right of the division symbol is another small image of the same car with a single red bounding box that encompasses both overlapping boxes from the previous image. Below this image is the word 'Union'.

Figure 3.7: *Intersection over Union (IoU)* formula for two overlapping bounding boxes.

Training an object detector requires a metric to evaluate the accuracy of the model. For regression problems *Mean Squared Error (MSE)* is a proven loss function to give an idea how far ground truth and predictions are apart. Classifiers usually use categorical crossentropy to ascertain if a label was correctly predicted. It is intuitive to ascertain whether a numerical value was predicted well or an image was labeled incorrectly. For the subject of object detection both the box position and the predicted class must be taken into account to evaluate the quality of a detector.

First, a metric is required to decide if an object was correctly detected or not. The previously introduced *IoU* is well suited for this task. Again, a threshold is used to classify a detection as *True Positive (TP)* or *False Positive (FP)*. For example IoU_{50} would require an *IoU* of at least 0.5 to be considered a correct prediction. Higher threshold values would therefore necessitate that ground truth and prediction are more similar to each other. Missed objects are classified *False Negative (FN)*, and *True Negatives (TNs)* are neglected since the metric is only concerned with the area surrounding objects.

From here, *Precision (P)* and *Recall (R)* can be derived. Equation 3.1 depicts how both values are calculated. *Precision* takes into account, what portion of all detected objects can be considered correct. *Recall* on the other hand determines what fraction of the ground truth objects was identified. Both metrics can be important depending on the use case. *Precision* is usually considered the more significant quantity to evaluate models with. However, some applications require a high *Recall* to avoid object missing

(e.g. autonomous driving, fault detection, etc.).

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad \text{and} \quad R = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (3.1)$$

By evaluating a dataset with both metrics for all classes respectively, *PR*-curves can be generated. An example of such a family of curves can be seen in Figure 3.8. The graph was generated by evaluating five classes with IoU_{50} . The *Area Under the Curve* (AUC) for a class is called *Average Precision* (AP). Hence, AP_{50}^{person} is a measure on how well a person can be detected with the IoU threshold set to 0.5. The bold blue curve is the average of all classes. Integrating its contour generates the *mean Average Precision* (*mAP*), which provides insight into the general model performance.

Figure 3.8: PR-curve family with five classes and an IoU of 0.5.

In literature usually two metrics are used to compare model performance. mAP_{50} evaluates the accuracy only at IoU_{50} , while $mAP_{50:5:95}$ averages over a range from 0.5 to 0.95 with step size 0.05. A more detailed overview over the introduced performance metrics can be found in [33].

3.4 Traffic Datasets

Training a *Deep Learning* model requires some sort of reference data to train the algorithm. Creating a custom dataset is a time and labor intensive task. Hence, reference datasets for common tasks became publicly available over time to facilitate an unobstructed research environment. There will always be an inherent bias within the data, for instance traffic images suffer from class imbalance due to the dominance of cars. Therefore, critical applications should always be trained on a variety of data sources.

Object detection models expect to be trained with bounding boxes as input. However, it is possible to use training data from the domain of object segmentation as well.

Such datasets use masks to determine an objects location within an image. A mask is defined by a finite number of points describing the objects contour. Figure 3.9 depicts the injective transformation from one format to the other. Limiting the point list to only consider the extrema in x and y direction, a bounding box can be deduced. It is worth mentioning, that there are several possibilities to define the coordinates of a bounding box. A common notation is the upper left corner coordinates along with height and width of the box (*COCO* scheme). Another popular format takes the box center, height and width all normalized to image size (*YOLO* scheme). Converting the box coordinates to the required notation is crucial for the training process.

Figure 3.9: Converting a mask annotation into a bounding box.

This allows for a wide range of possible datasets to be considered for training. In the following, several datasets which are particularly interesting for *ITS* applications are introduced. Table 3.1 gives an brief overview of the number of available frames and the annotation type.

	COCO	Cityscapes	KITTI	Citycam	Tampere
Frames	330 000	25 000	15 000	60 000	2000
Boxes	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓
Masks	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓

Table 3.1: Traffic dataset comparison.

3.4.1 Microsoft COCO

The Microsoft *Common Objects in Context (COCO)* dataset [34] is among the most popular ones in object detection. This is due to the fact, that the validation subset is commonly used for comparing the accuracy of object detectors. Hence, models are usually pretrained on this dataset. As the name suggests, there is no specialization for a certain type of objects. Similar to ImageNet [35] and the Open Images Dataset [36] a blend of common objects was annotated to enable models for universal purposes. From the 80 classes available several are useful for traffic applications. Figure 3.10 shows an example frame from the training subset. For annotations both bounding boxes and masks are available.

Figure 3.10: COCO training frame with traffic context.

3.4.2 Cityscape

Cityscape [37] uses image segmentation instead of object detection to define object boundaries. Figure 3.11 shows a panoptic annotation where each pixel has exactly one label associated. The data contains images from 50 European cities with a total frame count of 25 000. It is therefore significantly larger than the CamVid (101 images) [38] and Daimler Urban Segmentation dataset (500 images) [39].

Figure 3.11: Cityscape training frame Aachen with fine annotations.

3.4.3 KITTI

The *KITTI* dataset [40] was developed by the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology and hence uses traffic data from the German city of Karlsruhe (Figure 3.12). The data was generated by a driving car (ref. [41]), which was augmented with cameras among other sensors. The images are divided into separate categories to distinguish between different traffic scenarios (e.g. "City" and "Residential"). For each frame there are 2D and 3D bounding box annotations for various vehicle types and pedestrians. Additional metadata (e.g. object orientation, occlusion and truncation) is provided, which can be used to improve model training. The available dataset consists of roughly 15 000 images (ca. 80 000 objects) with an average resolution of 0.5 Megapixels.

Figure 3.12: KITTI training frame Karlsruhe [41].

3.4.4 Citycam

Figure 3.13 shows a frame from the Citycam dataset [42]. It uses data generated from traffic cams in New York City. Hence, each image has a fixed perspective, with dynamic objects. Each camera has a mask file to define the region of interest. Altogether, there are 60 000 labeled frames with a resolution of 352x240 pixels. The objects are annotated with 2D bounding boxes and ten different labels. Additional information like orientation, reidentification label, vehicle density and weather type are provided as well.

Figure 3.13: Citycam training frame camera 164

3.4.5 Tampere

The Tampere dataset is comprised of traffic camera images similar to Citycam. As the name suggests the data originates from Tampere, Finland [43]. There are various cameras available within the city perimeter [13]. They differ in resolutions and some are non stationary (panning cameras). For the time span between October 2019 and December 2020 traffic images were constantly scraped and archived for later analysis. Additional data from induction loops is available to optimize and evaluate traffic density detection algorithms.

From this raw data, two cameras with a subset of 1000 randomly selected images each were manually annotated. These frames are depicting the two major crossroads Lapintie (Pohjoiseen) (Figure 3.14a) and Rautatienkatu (Etelaan) (Figure 3.14b). The first has several traffic lights and crosswalks which present possible bottlenecks for

traffic flow while the later should allow a more unobstructed movement. Additionally, a bus stop is located at the right road side.

Figure 3.14: Tampere camera frames from two different intersections.

Figure 3.15a shows the geographic locations (red dots) of the traffic cameras in the city context of Tampere. Both are positioned at reasonably frequented roads near the city center. Figure 3.15b gives a close up view on where both camera are positioned and the direction they are facing. The viewing angle for Lapintie (Pohjoiseen) is directed city outward towards the closest freeway exit. Rautatienkatu (Etelaan) angle is nearly opposite facing more towards the city center. Both cameras are mounted for a bird’s eye view, hence looking down at angle on the scene. The first camera has a wide opening angle therefore focusing on close objects while the other has a sharp angle.

Figure 3.15: Camera positions in Tampere City with viewing angles [44].

The data was annotated as part of the *AI4DI* project by the OTH Amberg-Weiden. Labeling was performed with the *COCO* Annotator [45]. The browser tool supports both masks and bounding boxes to denote objects of interest. Mask annotations were used to make the dataset available for both object detection and segmentation research purposes. A labeling policy was imposed to ascertain consistent annotation quality despite of staff changes. The classes traffic light, person, bicycle, motorcycle, car, bus and truck are individually defined to circumvent ambiguities. For instance, the classes bicycle and motorcycle include the driver, which is therefore not separately marked as person. Furthermore, policies to handle occluded, truncated and concealed objects were devised. Additional best practices for edge cases were defined. This conceptual

formulation of the labeling task allowed for a self sufficient annotation pipeline with good result quality and time efficiency.

Figure 3.16: Visualization frame from dataset labeling policy.

The dataset is used as starting point for task layout, model training and evaluation throughout this document.

3.5 Transfer Learning

The concept of transfer learning [46] is the idea that knowledge for solving one task can be beneficial for figuring out a related assignment. This concept is derived from general knowledge transfer. For instance, a musician will find it easier to learn a new instrument compared a non-musically inclined person.

In the context of *Machine Learning*, model parameters can be considered the knowledge which has to be repurposed for a new assignment. From a mathematical perspective, these weights are a solution of a search space determined by an optimization algorithm such as gradient decent [47]. For a similar problem, these parameters can be used as a starting point to achieve faster convergence.

Deep Learning (DL) models usually consist of a great amount of parameters. Transfer learning can drastically decrease the time required for the algorithm to converge. Additionally, this technique can be used to improve accuracy by retraining a generic model for a dedicated purpose. The size of the training dataset can be reduced too.

A common application for classification tasks is retraining the model to recognize new classes. This is achieved by changing the last layer of the model (Figure 3.17) and starting a new training process. It is possible to freeze the weights and biases of the other layers, resulting in only the last layer to be trained. Therefore, training time and resource demand are being reduced.

Figure 3.17: Changing the last layer of an neuronal network to learn new classes.

Modern object detection models use an image classifier for generating a feature map to derive detections from. Such a *CNN* is usually trained beforehand on a classification image set. The model is later introduced as backbone into the object detector architecture. Here, transfer learning is used to obtain knowledge from one domain (classification) to a related area (object detection).

In the literature there is also the term *incremental learning* to describe the process of relearning a model with new data. Transfer learning is used as a generic term in this thesis.

Chapter 4

Microservices

The way software is developed and deployed has changed significantly over the recent years. Instead of relying on a local installation, more and more software capabilities are realized as web applications. This *Software as a Service (SaaS)* mindset entails rethinking the way software is structured. Instead of relying on a single monolithic application, several earmarked entities can collaborate with each other to offer the same functionality. This *Service Oriented Architecture (SOA)* approach gained significant popularity over the recent years. In software development, it is common to refactor functionality into reusable building blocks (methods, classes, modules, etc.). Microservices drive this idea further by encapsulating each responsibility into a self-containing unit. These building blocks can communicate with each other to reach the desired scope of functionality. Figure 4.1 depicts the idea of splitting a monolithic application into a service based approach. The users still interact via a general *User Interface (UI)* with the application and should not realize a difference. Hence, the change concerns primarily the backend.

Figure 4.1: Splitting a monolithic application into a Microservice structure.

4.1 Advantages and Critique

The topic of Microservices encounters different opinions. It is indisputable that this structural paradigm is already successfully utilized by several large software companies and becomes largely available for everyone by the means of *Amazon Web Services (AWS)* and Google Cloud. However, popular literature of this topic [48][49] mentions both the benefits and possible pitfalls of migrating to Microservices. Testimonials of issues regarding the execution can be found as well [50]. This section attempts to compile these dissonant standpoints and transfers these to the context of embedded intelligence.

Providing an application for a broad audience entails various challenges. A major trial is reliably coping with load peaks. In the past, it was feasible to increase computing resources (*CPU, RAM, etc.*) to meet a slowly increasing demand. Such vertical scaling is increasingly uneconomical with fluctuating resource utilization. Instead of regularly investing in more powerful hardware, additional resources are provided by dynamically distributing instances of the application to auxiliary computing systems. This load balanced horizontal scaling enables reliable applications in spite of strong variance in demand. Microservices make the subject of scaling even more efficient. Instead of replicating the entire application, only the parts which are in demand get assigned additional resources. In terms of heterogeneous edge *AI*, this entails distributing service to specialized hardware accelerators as shown in Chapter 2. It should be noted, an increasing number of services and replicas subsequently leads to a rise of internal data traffic. The infrastructure must therefore be able to supply enough bandwidth. This can be problematic for remote devices communicating wirelessly.

From a development point of view, Microservices simplify the process of expanding the functionalities of an application. Every feature is an independent unit which can therefore be developed without affecting other building blocks. By utilizing language agnostic protocols for internal communication, the services can be realized in an arbitrary language. With this freedom in development, new issues arise in regards to deployment and maintenance. The subject of testing becomes increasingly difficult for every new unit in the system. Communication between services over a network has to be considered when writing tests, which makes tracing the source of an error especially hard. As stated in [50] the application as a whole must be continuously tested in production to be able to cope with the building blocks being under constant development. Dealing with zero day vulnerabilities introduces additional overhead since every service could serve as a potential attack vector and must therefore be evaluated and patched if necessary.

Distributed systems have an increased probability for failures. An orchestration software such as Kubernetes can compensate for a variety of issues arising from a Microservice architecture. Still, fallback behavior has to be considered if a service is temporarily unavailable due to hardware failure or deployment issues. Setting up an application for a large user base where availability is a necessity generally requires administrative expenses that cannot be neglected.

Considering distributed edge hardware, for instance infrastructure elements, horizontal

scaling is the only feasibly way of increasing processing capabilities. Smart City scenarios become achievable if all available resources are used as efficiently as possible. This must happen in a highly dynamic fashion where participant can freely join and leave clusters for exchanging data and processing power. Such concepts can not be realized with traditional methods. Microservices are the most promising approach of integrating *AI* into everyday life. As stated, this comes along with several pitfalls to consider. Much work is required to setup reliable solutions which are straightforward and dynamically scalable.

4.2 Inter Service Communication

There is no prescribed way how Microservices have to interact with each other. Generally, communication is handled via a network link. However, shared memory, *Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE)* or mobile networks could be viable as well. For successful communication, the protocol stack must be known and interfaces have to be exposed properly.

There exists a variety of established possibilities to handle data exchange between services. *Representational State Transfer (REST)* [51] is the most prominent example. It enforces a list of constrains to enable unified communication interfaces. Such *RESTful Application Programming Interfaces (APIs)* offer well defined data transfer, which is most commonly handled by the *Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP)*. The *REST* paradigm follows a client-server architecture, where the server exposes endpoints to one or multiple clients. These handles can be used to create, read, update and delete (*CRUD*) corresponding data. This functionality is provided by the analogous *HTTP* methods *POST*, *GET*, *PUT* and *DELETE*. The handle represent the attribute one or more of these operations can be performed on. Listing 4.1 shows how such endpoint could look like. The *GET* method implies that data can be requested utilizing this interface. The subsequent path is used to access the resource from the host. A question mark signalizes the use of query parameters which are used to filter the response content.

```
1| GET /api/v1/deviceinfos?attribute=name
```

Listing 4.1: Example REST endpoint.

Data is commonly transferred as *JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)* payload within a *HTTP* frame. Listing 4.2 shows how the response to the previous *GET* request could look like. The queried attribute was returned to the client with the desired value.

```
1| {"name": "agx-xavier"}
```

Listing 4.2: Example JSON response.

A list of endpoints defines an *API*. It can be exposed with tools such as *OpenAPI* which give an overview of available interfaces and add further information for simplifying the process of building an application against the interface.

Such a *REST API* gives developers full control on what can be accessed by an external party. Therefore, possible security risks can be reduced by only excepting well defined

inputs. The interfaces can be expanded during the lifetime of an application and multiple *API* versions can coexist simultaneously to ascertain backward compatibility.

Considering data streaming, *REST* suffers from issues related to constant pooling and the overhead of *HTTP*. Here, a bidirectional websocket connection should be preferred. Ideally, the *API* exposes an interface to upgrade the connection once credentials were exchanged.

Other established paradigms for inter service communication are gRPC and GraphQL. The first was developed by Google to be able to cope with large amount of data. It uses *Remote Procedure Calls (RPCs)* and with protocol buffers (protobuf) for communication. GraphQL was designed by Facebook to reduce the number of request required to obtain specific data. It is therefore preferred for mobile applications.

4.3 Software Stack

Enabling *ML* applications in resource restricted areas become increasingly feasible by utilizing modern *AI* accelerators (ref. Chapter 2). However, every coprocessor utilizes different libraries and frameworks to expose its capabilities. The following introduces a software stack modern *AI* services can be built upon.

It is of major interest for software development to ensure unified interfaces. This in turn enables modular approaches with interchangeable and reusable building blocks. The *Open Neural Network Exchange (ONNX)* framework follows this approach and applies it to the context of *AI*. This allows developers to design their *ML* model in the framework of choosing (*Tensorflow*, *PyTorch*, etc.) and transfer it to a unified format for deployment. The *ONNX Runtime* can be utilized for inferring the model. It has the benefit of being lightweight for only incorporating components for executing, hence omitting everything required for training. The runtime can be compiled to support a large variety of execution providers. In the test setup *CPU*, *CUDA*, *TensorRT* and *OpenVINO* can be addressed by this framework alone. A wide support for operating systems, programming languages and hardware platforms contributing to universality of the *ONNX Runtime*.

As previously stated in Section 2.3, the *EdgeTPU* plays a special role as it does not comply with the flexible deployment of the *ONNX* format. A model has to be quantized and compiled into *TPU* instructions beforehand in order to utilize the underlying hardware. Therefore, a different runtime is required to make use of the coprocessor. The *TFLite* runtime is a subset of the *Tensorflow* framework with the focus set on edge deployment. Currently, inference can be performed with *ARM* and *x86* platforms on *CPU* and *EdgeTPU* utilizing a dynamic library (*libedgetpu.so*). The *TFLite* format is generally widely used for deployment on mobile (*Android*) and *IoT* devices.

This limits the number of supportable interfaces to two runtimes. An *AI* service must internally abstract these to realize a device agnostic interface. The models have to be available in the *ONNX* and *TFLite* format to cover all devices. A *REST* interface is used to expose functionality to other services. The *FastAPI* framework proved to be

well suited for this purpose.

Figure 4.2 depicts the application stack used throughout this document. The software is encapsulated within a Docker [52] image. This has the benefit of creating an isolated environment which is not bound to break due to changes on the host system. Hardware is passed into the container while ports are exposed to the outside. Everything necessary to execute the service is already included. This simplifies the process of deployment as only a container needs to be started.

Figure 4.2: Software stack for AI Microservices.

An important consideration for the subject of deploying containerized services in an edge environment is the size of the docker image to create instances from. This template has to be downloaded the first time a service is scheduled on a platform. Once available, everything must be loaded into memory which introduces additional overhead. Therefore, it is of great interest to design images to be as small as possible for creating fast and lightweight services. This principle contradicts with the idea of shipping large *AI* libraries together with the application. The Jetson platforms map some NVIDIA specific files from the host into the container to reduce this impact. However, the base image (14t-base:r32.6.1) still requires 636 MB of disk space. Adding everything else depicted in Figure 4.2 increases the size to 1.46 GB. For x86 systems, the image size is significantly larger (~7 GB) as all NVIDIA libraries are included. The EdgeTPU has the lowest memory footprint of all accelerators. TFLite Runtime and library require less than 10 MB together. Realizing a service with only TPU support could reduce the image size by a factor of ten on Jetson devices.

4.4 Inference Service

Machine Learning resolves about designing a mathematical model to address a particular issue. An *AI* service would provide the functionality necessary to utilize the model. It must expose well defined interfaces other services can interact with. Therefore, serving as a black box which performs a transformation on a data input.

The following inference service utilizes *YOLOv5* models to provide object detection functionality. It expects a binary *JPEG* file as input and transforms into an object list. Listing 4.3 shows a shorted *JSON* payload for image inference. A detection is defined by its bounding box, category and accuracy. Query parameters are used to set threshold values to reduce the count of results. Additionally, timings are returned to show how much time each processing step required.

```

1 | {
2 |   "detections": [
3 |     {
4 |       "bbox": [1, 568, 131, 164],
5 |       "category_id": 2,
6 |       "score": 0.9082638025283813
7 |     },
8 |     ...
9 |   ],
10 |   "timings": {
11 |     "img_load": 0.00007369299987658451,
12 |     "preprocessing": 0.016437952000160294,
13 |     "inference": 0.043543928999952186,
14 |     "postprocessing": 0.003177863000018988
15 |   }
16 | }

```

Listing 4.3: Shortened inference service response.

4.4.1 Architecture

An *AI* service revolves around the encapsulated model. Figure 4.3 shows how this translates to the software architecture. A model class poses as the core component of the *YOLOv5* inference service. Additional functionality is supplied by inheritance and injection.

Figure 4.3: Class diagram for the core functionality of the *YOLOv5* inference service.

The abstract *BaseModel* class describes subsequent steps for a data processing pipeline. A model performs operation on data tensors, which have to be supplied in a fixed

format. In a first step data must be transformed to comply with the model restrictions. For *YOLOv5* this involves image scaling and a type transformation from `int8` to `float32`. What follows is the actual inference which returns a list of numerical tensors. In a last step, these values are converted into a more readable form. For the inference service this implies the transformation into an object list by utilizing *NMS*, thresholds and reverse transformations. The class contains additional meta data such as name and file hash. A session object is created after the model is loaded.

The functionality for data pre- and postprocessing is handled by a *DataProcessor* class. It is injected into a *BaseModel* class which provides the interfaces for the desired transformations. The class exposes variables for parametrization the inference process.

Supporting both *ONNX* and *TFLite* runtime requires abstraction by different child classes. A factory pattern is used for deciding which class gets instantiated. A model file and the deployment device are used as indicators to create a *BaseModel* instance of the appropriate runtime or throw an error if the requested configuration is not available.

4.5 Edge Benchmark Service

Benchmarking describes the process of generating key figures to compare systems. This is particularly useful for making informed decisions when purchasing hardware for a specific purpose. By obtaining concrete numbers, it is possible to determine if a product is faster or more efficient than another. How such numbers should be generated is a controversial topic. Vendors usually proclaim their products peak performance through (floating point) *Operations Per Second (OPS)*. This number is an indicator on how many calculations could theoretically be performed by the hardware in one second. For example, the Coral Edge *TPU* is marketed with a peak performance of four trillion *OPS*. However, there are several issues with such a metric. It is hard to determine of how many operations a certain task consists. Moreover, how well optimized the assignment is to be processed by the hardware. Such could lead to a scenario, where a device with higher peak *OPS* performs worse than a lower ranked one.

Counteracting these synthetical key figures, application oriented benchmarks are performed to provide more informed insight. The basic idea is to measure tangible quantities for common tasks. Such could be the time required to compress a large file, *Frames Per Second (FPS)* for rendering a video or the average energy consumption of realistic idle and load scenarios. Instead of comparing intangible numbers with each other, multiple application related key figures are given which can be weighted by personal preference.

Considering the subject of *AI*, the tasks used for comparison would be the inference of common *Machine Learning* models. Hence, a benchmark was set up to characterize object detection model performance of modern *AI* accelerators.

4.5.1 Related Work

There exists a wide variety of *Deep Learning* benchmarks to choose from. Some software was developed to target a special research area. For instance XTREME [53] and GLUE [54] are exclusive to the field of *Natural Language Processing (NLP)*. Considering more generalized benchmarks, Fathom [55] and DAWNbench [56] presented a promising approach.

MLCommons is a group effort to improve the experience of *Machine Learning* by offering best practices, datasets and benchmarks. They provide MLPerf, an open source suite to perform training [57] and inference [58] evaluation. This software became a de facto standard for performance comparison in *High Performance Computing (HPC)*. MLPerf fulfills the seven prime benchmark characteristics of Relevance, Representativeness, Equity, Repeatability, Cost-effectiveness, Scalability and Transparency, which were compiled in [59]. It covers the *ML* areas of vision, speech, language and commerce by offering proven models of this field. Custom implementations are accepted in a separate 'Open' ranking. MLPerf's core metric is latency, which is generated by reassessing the 90th percentile time delay of a query scenario. Power measurements can be submitted as well.

The topic of edge computing differs significantly from *HPC*. Energy demand has a far greater impact on the feasibility of an application. Additionally, the underlying infrastructure is far more heterogeneous and prone to change. Considering this, a generic benchmark such as MLPerf is not ideal to allow for an optimal evaluation. Some attempts [60, 61] were made to assess the performance of novel edge *AI* platforms. However, no publicly available software was released. This changed with the release of MLPerf Tiny [62] at the end of this research. While primarily targeted at *Artificial Intelligence of Things (AIoT)*, the basic requirements are present for adapting an edge workload.

4.5.2 Architecture

The benchmark service designed in the context of this thesis is an extension to the inference service. Its main objective is to characterize the performance *AI* application for a certain configuration. Therefore, obtaining several key figures which capture the dynamic and static behavior of a deployment in an edge environment. Such an insight could further be used to make an informed decision for platform selection and optimal task placement.

The class diagram in Figure 4.4 depicts the software architecture of the benchmark service. Again, a `BaseModel` object presents the center of the application. It contains the same functionality as the inference service implementation. This allows to directly translate the insights of the benchmark to the subsequent deployment. A `StubModel` was introduced for idle characterization without initializing any hardware.

The measurement process is handled by the `Profiler` class. It acts as decorator for a `BaseModel`. Measurements are started, stopped, stored and dumped by this class. Verbose meta data is added describing soft- and hardware configuration of the platform

allowing to reproduce and comparing results at a later time. Energy measurements are realized by a `EnergyMonitorClass` serving as plugin for the Profiler. It communicates with an energy monitor service running on a separate device within the test setup.

A `Scenarios` class defines schemes to test specific service behavior. Idle characterizes the system without load. The transient nature is evaluated by the startup method and inference is responsible the steady behavior.

Figure 4.4: Class diagram for the benchmark utility service core.

Listing 4.4 shows a shortened benchmark dump for the idle scenario with energy measurements. The `device` node lists properties, describing hardware and software state of the platform during the benchmark. This includes connected hardware accelerators, operating system and library versions to recreate the measurements at a later point of time.

Multiple scenarios can be performed during a benchmark process. A counter is used to capture the chronological order and ensure unique keys. A scenario can contain meta data such as the units for different measurement time series data, the methods used during execution, model properties, number of repetitions, doc string and return status. Every function profiled during a scenario (e.g. `sleep`) is represented as node with time series properties. The `time_s` values are measured on the platform itself depicting the execution duration from start to end. The other entries are `EMS` measurements

containing instantaneous voltage and current values as well as time stamps to precisely recreate the time series for evaluation.

Issues regarding performance or instability can be difficult to trace when utilizing a complex software stack. A *logging* node was therefore introduced, which captures notifications generated from lower software layers. These messages can be used afterwards for debugging unexpected outcomes.

```

1 | {
2 |   "device": {
3 |     "name": "agx-xavier",
4 |     "python": "3.6.9",
5 |     "system": "Linux-4.9.253-tegra-aarch64-with-Ubuntu-18.04-bionic",
6 |     "arch": "aarch64",
7 |     "is_jetson": true,
8 |     "tpu_usb": true,
9 |     "vpu_usb": true,
10 |    "tflite": "2.5.0.post1",
11 |    "libedgetpu": "16.0",
12 |    "onnx_runtime": "1.9.1",
13 |    "onnx_runtime_dev": "GPU-OPENVINO_MYRIAD",
14 |    "openvino": "2021.4.1",
15 |    "cuda": "10.2.300",
16 |    "cudnn": "8.2.1",
17 |    "trt": "8.0.1",
18 |    "trt_fp16": false,
19 |    "trt_int8": false,
20 |    "trt_cache": false
21 |  },
22 |  "0-idle": {
23 |    "meta": {
24 |      "unit": [
25 |        "time_s",
26 |        "current_ma",
27 |        "voltage_mv",
28 |        "time_ns"
29 |      ],
30 |      "method": ["sleep"],
31 |      "scenario": "idle",
32 |      "model": {
33 |        "name": "yolov5n_v6_640",
34 |        "hash": "530a5062a7856279cbf6bb88e103a8aad71203526b421917d097441273780ab4",
35 |        "exec_providers": ["CPUExecutionProvider"]
36 |      },
37 |      "data": [],
38 |      "turns": 1,
39 |      "doc": "sleep for a specific time interval",
40 |      "return": true
41 |    },
42 |    "sleep": {
43 |      "time_s": [100.08543226699112],
44 |      "current_ma": [[...]],
45 |      "voltage_mv": [[...]],
46 |      "ts_ns": [[...]]
47 |    },
48 |    "scenario_dur_time_s": 101.76509860495571
49 |  },
50 |  "logging": [...]
51 | }

```

Listing 4.4: Shortened benchmark dump for idle scenario.

Chapter 5

Pipeline Evaluation

This chapter intends to build different Micro Service pipelines based on the previously introduced inference and benchmark services. The objectives are to obtain key indicators for the performance of different edge accelerators, evaluate the impact of transfer learning on model accuracy and demonstrate how a pipeline for traffic density estimation could be beneficial for smart city applications. Furthermore, concepts are proposed to increase the functionality and robustness of the service pipeline.

The assembly utilizes a *YOLOv5n* model in revision 6.0. The *Nano* type was chosen due to its low number of parameters (1.9M). This in turn leads to a relative small size of ~ 8 MB (floating point) and ~ 2 MB (quantized) which is ideal for embedded applications. Similarly to a previously released paper [63] all measurements were performed on a Jetson Xavier AGX with a Google Coral Edge *TPU* and an Intel *NCS2* attached.

5.1 Performance Characterization

Section 4.5 has given an insight into the important role performance metrics have for comparability. In the following, both timing characteristics and energy demand are empirically determined. This is achieved by setting up a benchmark pipeline as shown in Figure 5.1. A reference image (Lapintie (Pohjoiseen)) is used throughout the measurements as default input with a batch size of one. The benchmark service acts as decorator for the inference service as conceptualized in Section 4.5.2. It is responsible for measuring the execution time of the individual function calls. Additionally, trigger signals are used for interacting with the *EMS* service which continuously measures voltage and current of the appliance.

The benchmark is based on the software stack of Section 4.3. Results are being compared according to the execution provider. These are namely *CPU*, *CUDA (GPU)*, *TensorRT (GPU)*, *OpenVINO (VPU)* and *TFLite (TPU)*. All measurements have a support of at least 100 repetitions. A detailed benchmark report with all numerical data can be found in the Appendix.

Figure 5.1: Service pipeline for performance benchmark.

5.1.1 Timing Evaluation

There are three important time metrics to consider when deploying a *Deep Learning* application. At first, the model has to be loaded from disk into the memory of the device executing it. This *load* phase τ_l is important, if the designated use requires fast availability or when models are exchanged regularly. Similarly, the first inference often takes longer to finish than subsequent instances. Depending on the execution provider, this *warmup* τ_w can introduce a significant additional latency. Last but not least, the *inference* phase τ_i gives an insight of the steady behavior of the system. The metric enables a throughput estimation for the later application and is especially relevant for long running scenarios, where the transient behavior is negligible.

Table 5.1 gives a breakdown how long the *YOLOv5n* model load and warmup phase took respectively. *TFLite* performs best of all five providers. This is most likely due to the fact that the model was precompiled to run on the *TPU* as described in Section 2.3. *ONNX* models on the other hand are modified at runtime to be executable on the desired hardware. *CPU* execution does not require device specific modification and is therefore loading fast as well. On the other hand, *TensorRT* requires several minutes to load the model. This appears to be a *YOLOv5* specific issue which could already be observed in [63]. The *TensorRT* provider rebuilds the model into *engines* to increase the overall performance. This process is probably not optimized for the *YOLOv5* architecture. Engine caching can be used to partially circumvent this issue. By utilizing this technique, engines are prebuilt offline and loaded later on demand. It was disabled during this investigation to show the load times for a fresh deployment.

	Load Time τ_l	Warmup Time τ_w
CPU	0.153	0.280
OpenVINO	2.970	0.281
TFLite	0.009	0.174
CUDA	3.764	2.949
TensorRT	189.948	0.053

Table 5.1: *YOLOv5n* load and warmup timings in seconds for different providers.

Considering the average inference time for each provider (Figure 5.2), *TensorRT* is able to vindicate its long startup time by gaining a two time speed up compared to regular *CUDA-GPU* inference. With a latency of under 100ms real time vehicle tracking could be a viable application for this setup. The *TPU* performance is significantly

worse considering inference speeds of roughly 20 ms are possible [63]. This again is due to the fact that the *YOLOv5* architecture is not optimized to be executed on this hardware. The first 224 operations of the model are actually processed by the *EdgeTPU* while the remaining 60 instructions fall back to *CPU* inference. This last 20 % consists largely of *MAC* operations, which do not perform well on a regular processor. A detailed quantization log can be seen in Listing 6.1 in the Appendix. *OpenVINO* has a slight benefit over the *CPU* execution provider, which is probably caused by recent improvements of the *ONNX* runtime. However, the speedup is too marginal to justify the usage of a Movidius *VPU*.

Figure 5.2: Average inference time τ_i .

5.1.2 Energy and Power Demand

The power consumption of the device is monitored continuously during several repetitions of the scenario of interest. This procedure was chosen to compensate for the relatively slow 50 Hz sample rate of the *EMS*. Figure 5.3 depicts how the measurements were conducted. The Jetson AGX Xavier with attached *TPU* and *VPU* serves as *Unit Under Test (UUT)* for the setup. It is connected to a Raspberry Pi 3 hosting the *EMS* service. Trigger signals are used to start and stop measurements. The Pi is constantly buffering instantaneous current and voltage values broadcasted by the *EMS* via the *UART* interface. After each scenario, the instantaneous active power measurements are saved alongside the timing values.

Figure 5.3: EMS measurement block diagram.

As power is continuously measured while constantly repeating the scenario, a stochastic contemplation is necessary to properly evaluate the time series. Figure 5.4 depicts a *Kernel Density Estimation (KDE)* plot of 100 s idle time. The data is not ideally Gaussian distributed. Moreover, the plot is a superimposition of several different distributions.

Such a behavior is expected as the *UUT* is a complex system with different components and a scheduler running background tasks. For this evaluation the mean is considered to be the key figure of interest. Looking at the entire plot can be helpful for designing the application's power supply to handle peaks.

Figure 5.4: KDE plot for platform idle power consumption.

The average idle power of the platform was measured at ~ 8.3 W, which includes power losses within the wires and the connected accelerators. Cable losses are only relevant when comparing different platforms with each other, hence they are neglected. The *VPU* idle power was previously determined [63] at 0.684 W while the *TPU* required 0.362 W. The real power consumption of a device during a scenario can be determined with Equation 5.1. P_0 is the raw measurement and P_{dev} can either be P_{vpu} , P_{tpu} or 0 W depending on the accelerator in use. This method is not ideal, as the idle value of *CPU* and *GPU* is not determinable for the Jetson Xavier. Therefore, for all upcoming calculations P_{dev} are ignored. In other words, it evaluates how much more power is needed compared to idling.

$$\Delta P = P_0 - P_{idle} + P_{dev} \quad (5.1)$$

Table 5.2 shows how high this offset turns out for every provider within each phase. It is notable that *GPU* utilizing has the highest impact on power consumption. *TensorRT* inference stands out the most. The *TRT* engines seem to better utilize the *GPU* capabilities, therefore increasing the power demand. Load and warmup are primarily handled by the *CPU* which results in moderate power draw. Figure 5.5 depicts the normalized *KDE* plots for all providers. The *GPU* distributions significantly differ from the other devices. *CPU*, *TPU* and *VPU* are almost congruent due to similar shapes and peak values. In addition, the measurements are limited to a narrow band. *CUDA* and *TensorRT* on the other hand operating under a large standard derivation. A power supply must be able to handle such large load fluctuations continuously.

	Load	Warmup	Inference
CPU	0.908	1.780	0.866
OpenVINO	1.492	1.871	0.715
TFLite	0.555	0.902	0.778
CUDA	1.631	2.112	5.919
TensorRT	2.513	2.472	7.903

Table 5.2: Mean power offset for different providers in Watt.

Figure 5.5: Normalized inference power KDE plot.

From an economical point of view, energy consumption is a very significant metric. It can be used to estimate the lifetime of a battery driven application or predict the energy cost required to run a system continuously. The following considers the energy consumption per inference for the *UUT*. In practical, this metric could be used to characterize a long running application, where the transient becomes negligible. The results were calculated using Equation 5.2 with the values from Table 5.2 and Figure 5.2.

$$E_{inf} = \Delta P_{inf} \cdot t_{inf} \tag{5.2}$$

Figure 5.6 shows that the energy consumption for the providers does not vary as much as the speed and power key figures. This implies that for faster inference speed an increase in power consumption is expected and vice versa. However, optimizations in both hardware (*EdgeTPU*) and software (*TensorRT*) enable a significant increase of the overall efficiency.

Figure 5.6: Energy required to perform one inference for each provider.

Considering the subject of *AI* task scheduling, model profiles could be used for decision making. Figure 5.7 depicts how the previously generated key figures can be used to characterize a system composed of platform, accelerator and model in regards of inference count and energy consumption.

In Figure 5.7a it is shown how many inferences are performed over time in a half logarithmic plot. Each curve is piecewise defined by time intervals, consisting of the

load τ_l (zero inferences), warmup τ_w (first inference) and steady phase τ_i (subsequent inferences). The formula in Equation 5.3 shows how the values were calculated. Briefly put, once the transient phase is completed, a linear increase of inferences can be observed over time.

$$N(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } t < \tau_l + \tau_w \\ 1 + \left\lfloor \frac{t - (\tau_l + \tau_w)}{\tau_i} \right\rfloor & \text{if } t \geq \tau_l + \tau_w \end{cases}, t \in \mathbb{R}_0^+ \quad (5.3)$$

The intersection points are the of most interest for rescheduling a task from one provider or platform to another. For instance, an application could start a *TFLite* service which is available almost instantly and has a moderate inference speed. Simultaneously, a *TensorRT* instance is started. If the service is needed for more than 4 minutes, rescheduling from *TFLite* to *TensorRT* can be considered to increase the overall throughput.

Figure 5.7b considers the additional energy demand for continuously running *AI* interferences. Equation 5.4 was used to generate the full logarithmic graph. All lines have a y-offset (E_l) representing the load phase, which is the minimum energy required for deployment. The first inference is again regarded separately. Subsequent runs contribute a linear growth in energy demand.

$$\Delta E(n) = \begin{cases} \Delta E_l & \text{if } n = 0 \\ \Delta E_l + \Delta E_w + (n - 1)\Delta E_i & \text{if } n \geq 1 \end{cases}, n \in \mathbb{N}_0 \quad (5.4)$$

It can be seen that *TFLite* performs best throughout the entire period of observation. Hence, rescheduling would not be beneficial. For *CUDA* on the other hand, switching at about 5000 inferences to *TensorRT* would reduce the overall energy demand. Additionally, this rescheduling would increase the inference speed as well.

Figure 5.7: Model profiles for a potential scheduling scheme.

In conclusion, small object detection services are feasible on embedded platform. Edge accelerators are a good approach for providing sufficient speed with a low energy

footprint. The *EdgeTPU* achieved good results here while the *NCS2* was only slightly better than the *ARM CPU*. If this is due to lack of software optimization or the hardware itself must be evaluated in future research. If real time processing is required, only *GPU* inference can be considered suitable for this setup. However, the additional speed is obtained by a higher startup latency and increased demand on the power supply. The subject of task scheduling becomes increasingly harder when considering different types of hardware. The introduced model profiles could serve as input for an intelligent scheduling algorithm to make the best use of the available resources.

5.2 Transfer Learning Detection Accuracy

The benefits of transfer learning were previously elaborated in Section 3.5. It has to be evaluated whether model retraining can be beneficial for the performance of small edge detectors. This is determined by setting up a service pipeline for accuracy evaluation. Figure 5.8 shows the consecutive steps which need to be executed. The custom labeled Tampere City dataset (ref. Section 3.4.5) serves as reference data source for this section. All raw evaluation images are passed to the inference service which generates an object list from the detections. The confidence threshold was fixed to 30 % during all tests along with an *IoU* of 60 % for the *NMS* which was performed on all classes together. All models used were in the *ONNX* format with 32 bit floating point precision and the *CUDA* execution provider was utilized for the inference. Last but not least, an accuracy evaluation service is responsible for comparing the detected objects with the ground truth labels. The metric used for accuracy comparison is the mAP_{50} score introduced in Section 3.3.

Figure 5.8: Service pipeline for accuracy evaluation.

The baseline *YOLOv5* model comes with pretrained *COCO* weights. For transfer learning the three datasets *COCO*, *Cityscapes* and *Tampere* (only training data) from Section 3.4 were used. *COCO6* refers to a subset of the original dataset which only contains the six classes relevant for this evaluation. The idea behind this approach is that a small model could better utilize its sparse number of parameters if the class count is reduced. Transfer learning was performed on the same model consecutively with different datasets. This was done to ascertain whether a model accuracy can benefit from familiarizing with a diverse set of application specific data. The training was performed utilizing the scripts provided by the *YOLOv5* repository. All models were trained with a batch size of 256 on a *NVIDIA Tesla V100-32GB* for a duration of 100 epochs and a fixed reception field of 640 px^2 .

Figure 5.9 shows the number of label instances for all three datasets. All candidates show a great imbalance between the classes. *COCO6* has a clear bias towards the person class, while *Cityscapes* and *Tampere* dominantly contain cars. Additionally, *Cityscapes* does not offer traffic lights. This is due to the masks of the original dataset have no instance segmentation for this class. Hence, it was not possible to obtain bounding boxes for this class.

Figure 5.9: Label instances for each dataset.

The three datasets were used in a training pipeline (Figure 5.10) to observe how transfer learning impacts the model accuracy. The original weights serve as baseline for the subsequent evaluation. Up to three retraining steps were performed one after the other using permutations of the data sets to derive different weights.

Figure 5.10: Transfer Learning pipeline for YOLOv5n model.

Table 5.3 gives an insight on how transfer learning effects the prediction accuracy for the Tampere evaluation data. The row labels describing the datasets used subsequently for retraining. For instance, *COCO6.Cityscapes* shows the results of the *YOLOv5n* baseline model, which was retrained on the reduced *COCO* dataset and further trained on *Cityscapes*. The columns show the mAP_{50} for each class as well as the mean value averaged over all classes.

	mean	person	bicycle	car	truck	bus	traffic light
COCO (Baseline)	0.203	0.181	0.050	0.430	0.117	0.430	0.012
COCO6	0.258	0.258	0.050	0.449	0.163	0.554	0.074
Cityscapes	0.103	0.102	0.057	0.328	0.000	0.130	0.000
Tampere	0.367	0.458	0.000	0.718	0.081	0.228	0.720
Cityscapes_Tampere	0.481	0.499	0.182	0.748	0.196	0.475	0.787
COCO6_Cityscapes	0.092	0.108	0.052	0.317	0.017	0.055	0.000
COCO6_Tampere	0.529	0.515	0.076	0.743	0.389	0.661	0.789
COCO6_Cityscapes_Tampere	0.540	0.560	0.205	0.760	0.281	0.610	0.823

Table 5.3: COCO mAP_{50} score for Tampere validation dataset.

Reducing the number of classes (COCO6) appears to generally increase the model precision by a reasonable margin. This insight is beneficial for deploying models into an application specific environment. Instead of manually creating a custom dataset, a subset of a generic dataset could be used to achieve better accuracy. Future publications have to evaluate if this effect is reproducible for larger models.

Models which were last trained with the Cityscapes dataset perform worse than the baseline model. However, when applying further transfer learning with other dataset, a general improvement can be observed. For instance, the *Cityscapes_Tampere* model yields significant better results than the ‘Tampere’ model. This especially holds true for under represented classes. Even the traffic light class performs better, although no new instances are present in the dataset. It seems the model gains a better understanding of what constitutes an object, when being confronted with more divers instances. Therefore, the model which was trained consecutively with all three datasets performed best of all.

In general, the best transfer learning performance is achieved, when introducing the model to data of the subsequent field of application. All models which were trained on the Tampere dataset showed significantly better results. Hence, creating training data for the later deployment can be a worthwhile expense. As shown here, not much example data is required to obtain reasonable improvements.

Rather peculiar is the low precision of traffic light detections for COCO models. It is obvious that the Cityscape dataset can not add any beneficial insight for this class. However, COCO6 should have enough examples to perform decently. Figure 5.11 gives a bit insight on this issue. It appears that the model is only able to detect road traffic lights with an active non occluded light state (red, yellow, green). A majority of the instances in the evaluation dataset are pedestrian traffic lights or have no visible light. The issue is therefore most likely caused by COCO providing not enough diversification for this particular class. Additionally, the depicted traffic lights only consist of very few pixels and are therefore hard to detect.

In summary, transfer learning can significantly improve the performance of a *DL* solution. Additionally, only a fraction of data is required compared to traditional training. Using data from the subsequent application has the greatest positive impact

Figure 5.11: Traffic light detections for COCO6 model (blue) and missed instances (red).

for the overall accuracy. The procedure enables the utilization of smaller models while still maintaining decent precision. Consequently, transfer learning could become standard procedure for *AIoT* in the upcoming years.

5.3 Traffic Density Estimation and Prediction

Traffic density estimation describes the process of obtaining information about the approximate number of vehicles on a road segment at a specific point of time. The value directly correlates with traffic flow. It can be considered a measure of capacity, where a congestion represents an overload of the available resources. Gaining such insight formerly involved a high amount of financial investments and some degree of uncertainty. For instance, employing workers to write down type and number of vehicles during a time interval is error prone and not reasonably scalable. Loop detectors on the other hand are more reliable, however installation and maintenance is costly and labor intensive. Furthermore, information about the vehicle type is not easy to obtain. Other sensor types such as radar and lidar suffer from issues as well. Utilizing traffic cameras seems to be a reasonable approach for acquiring the desired information. They are already omnipresent at major arterial roads and can easily be upgraded with embedded computing units to perform object detection tasks locally at a low price. In cases where a high degree of certainty is required, sensor fusion can be utilized to improve results by considering different data sources.

Having a grasp on the general traffic density offers the potential for a variety of optimizations with benefits for the society as a whole. Cities and highways could be restructured or traffic rerouted using smart traffic signs to avoid congestion. This reduces overall travel time and fuel consumption. Public transport could be promoted as alternative for heavily crowded routes to reduce the number of vehicles and therefore to lower emissions.

5.3.1 Related Work

The topic of traffic density estimation and prediction can be considered a subject of control theory. As shown in [64] road segments can be modeled as systems which influence the vehicle flow rate. Such state models can be used to simulate scenarios which in turn helps urban planning to design efficient and robust infrastructure. Nowadays, it is more common to use statistical [65, 66], Kalman filtering [67, 68] and deep learning based predictors [66, 68–72] as they are more flexible to use.

The matter of reliably obtaining traffic density data to fit such models was a difficult endeavor not too long ago. The first attempts on evaluating image footage, generally utilized methods such as background subtraction with thresholding for efficiently calculating the number of vehicles in a frame [73]. The advent of *Deep Learning* offered new concepts for analyzing image data. Instead of relying on convoluted and error prone image manipulation, a model could be trained to automatically extract knowledge from image data. Object detection approaches were not popular at first as models were far more resource intensive and did not perform well on low resolution traffic footage [74]. In [75], a regressive and an encoder-decoder approach were proposed to generate density maps from an input frame. Integrating over this output returned an estimate for the vehicle count. As object detection models improved over time, a renewed interest for applying them in *ITS* research could be observed. In [76], a Faster *R-CNN* network was used to detect vehicles in aerial image footage. Single shot detectors introduced a significant performance boost which made them particularly interesting. [77] shows the feasibility of running *YOLO* based vehicle detection on embedded platforms utilizing the *NCS2* accelerator for inference. A detailed study comparing different *SOTA* object detection models (*YOLOv4*, *EfficientDet*, and *CenterNet*) for their suitability of vehicle counting and tracking can be found in [78]

A different approach for estimating traffic density was proposed in [79]. The vehicles in a mobile traffic scenario count the number of neighboring vessels and derive an individual density estimate from this count. Such an idea could be expanded if having vehicles communicate with each other in micro clusters to agree on some consensus value. This would enable traffic density estimation for rural areas where stationary sensors would not be cost efficient.

5.3.2 Evaluation

Object lists obtained one camera frame alone do not have much expressive power. More insight can be gained by analyzing time series data obtained from processing an image stream over time. Such a temporal difference considerations can be used to detect seasonal components within the data. Whether such periodicity is given has an impact on the predictability of the traffic flow. Well contained time series data could be used for fitting stochastic or *Machine Learning* based forecasting models. A difference function between prediction and real time evaluation offers the potential to quickly detect anomalies such as congestion.

The following shows box plots for the car count per minute averaged over the duration of the subsequent hour. Therefore, the first box represents the car density per minute between 00:00am and 00:59am during a month of collected data. Separate graphs were generated to show a distinction between weekday and weekend traffic. The detection task was performed using a YOLOv5l model which was retrained using the COCO6, Cityscapes and Tampere dataset. The larger model was chosen to suppress false classification which could lead to a misinterpretations in the evaluation process.

Figure 5.12a shows the car density per minute during working days for the Lapintie (Pohjoiseen) intersection in November 2021. The vehicle count jumps significantly up between 06:00am and 09:00am were most people drive to work. A median value of about 14 cars is held until the end of work at about 18:00pm. It afterwards linearly declines to a nightly base level of about 3 cars per minute. The graph could be approximated by a trapezoidal shape profile for making very crude predictions. No peaks in vehicles can be observed in the morning and the evening. Either rush hour spikes are negated due to the relative centric position of the intersection a saturation point is reached, were no more cars can fit into the observation area. Figure 5.12a depicts the car density during the weekend. The median profile is more triangularly shaped and differs therefore significantly from the weekday behavior. The base level at around 4.5 cars per minute is higher while the peak median stays about the same. The change in density happens a lot slower during the weekend.

Figure 5.12: Car density for Lapintie (Pohjoiseen) during November 2021.

Figure 5.13 shows the same data analysis as before for the Rautatienkatu (Etelaan) intersection. Similar median profiles can be observed, however the overall number of vehicles is significantly lower. Moreover, a high standard deviation can be observed during the day on both the weekend and working days. Such noise makes the creation of prediction models far more difficult.

The heatmaps in Figure 5.14 depict the data used for generating the previous figures. The rows of the matrices representing a day of observation, while columns exemplify the time of day. The color is used to express the number of cars counted during a time interval of one minute. This presentation method allows to detect anomalies which

Figure 5.13: Car density for Rautatienkatu (Etelaan) during November 2021.

would otherwise be lost due to averaging. One such irregularity is the long period of high traffic density during noon at November 18th. A reasonable explanation for this would be a congestion caused by some kind of accident. However, inspecting the raw camera data showed a lack of images for this time frame. The algorithm used for generating the heat maps interpolated the time series with the last value available. For a future smart city scenario in which such data could be used as a basis for autonomous decision making, this could have unforeseeable consequences.

Figure 5.14: Car count occurrence heat maps November 2021.

Another irregularity can be observed at November 21th. While Figure 5.14a shows nothing out of the ordinary, an increase in car count can be observed at the intersection of Rautatienkatu (Etelaan) during noon. Analyzing the raw image footage shows an uncharacteristic high amount of parking vehicles (ref. Figure 5.15). The reason for this spike in demand for parking space could not be determined with high level of certainty. Possible explanations could be an open Sunday or church service in the nearby Tampere Cathedral.

Figure 5.15: Rautatienkatu (Etelaan) intersection November 21th at 15:56pm.

The seasonal effects observed in Figures 5.12 and 5.13 can be seen in the occurrence heat map as well. The second matrix is significantly darker than the first which reflects an overall lower vehicle count. At the weekends traffic takes longer to build up which results in a periodic pattern for the columns reflecting the morning hours. A similar behavior can be observed for the night traffic. At the weekends more vehicles are counted at late hours.

Object detection allows for analyzing spacial properties in a temporal context by considering the bounding box positions of subsequent frames. Figure 5.16 shows both intersections with an car traffic flow overlay, generated with traffic data from November 2021. The images were created by adding and averaging bounding box areas. A lighter color reflects a high vehicle density over time. Darker regions have low or none occurrences of the analyzed class. Therefore, parking vehicles are the brightest spots in the images while sidewalks and the sky are colored dark.

(a) Lapintie (Pohjoiseen)

(b) Rautatienkatu (Etelaan)

Figure 5.16: Car traffic flow overlays for November 2021.

In Figure 5.16a, the impact of the traffic lights can clearly be seen. Behind the pedestrian crosswalks, traffic backlogs are rather common. The horizontally passing street does not seem to suffer from such an effect. This could imply that the road (Satakunnankatu) is prioritized and therefore has longer green periods. Vehicles turning left leaving an imprint as they inevitably have to slow down. In Figure 5.16b, no traffic lights are

visible, therefore a smoother traffic flow can be observed. Backlogs are primarily caused by waiting periods at intersections. The right lane going city inward is significantly darker than the left lane going outward. In particular the left turn lane increases the time spent in queue.

In Figure 5.17, the previous analysis was performed considering the occurrences of pedestrians. As to be expected, the streets show a darker hue, showing absence of this class while sidewalks have a lighter shade. It can be seen that the first crossroad is far less popular for people than the second one. This is most likely due the road in Figure 5.17b leading city inward towards the train station while the other intersection is a bit more remotely positioned. The cluster of people at the right side is caused a bus stop, hence people are gathering there throughout the day.

Figure 5.17: Person traffic flow overlays for November 2021.

5.3.3 Forecasting Model

The previous studies have already shown that there are repeating patterns in the data that allow some predictability. In the following, an attempt is made to develop a mathematical model that is able to make accurate predictions about the future hourly development of traffic density. Figure 5.18 shows how such a predictor could be used for extending the pipeline. The forecasts could enable early congestion detection and routing optimizations.

Figure 5.18: Service pipeline for predicting future traffic density.

The time series in Figure 5.19 depicts the car density per minute during November 2021 at the Lapintie (Pohjoiseen) intersection. A average filter of length 60 Min was used to smoothen out noisy components of the data. The weekends are highlighted with an orange overlay. As one can see, these sections have a more triangular shape

compared to working days. Not so obvious is a small phase shift caused by the delayed ramp up times during the weekend. The previously observed irregularity at November 18th can be detected here as well.

Figure 5.19: Car density for Lapintie (Pohjoiseen) during November 2021.

Analyzing the waveform shows an obvious periodicity with a frequency of one day (24 lags). Such seasonality can be recognized in the *Autocorrelation Function (ACF)* (ref. Section 5.3.3) as well. No kind of overall trend is noticeable through the duration of the month. The *augmented Dickey Fuller test (ADF)* [80] confirms this observation by returning a p-value of 0.82×10^{-3} . The value is far below the significance threshold of 5%, so that the time series can be considered stationary.

Considering developing a prediction model for the time series, further analysis is required. The plot in Section 5.3.3 shows a decaying property of the *ACF*. This could be an indication for using a *Moving Average (MA)* process. Looking at the *Partial Autocorrelation Function (PACF)* in Section 5.3.3, up to ten significant lags for an *Auto Regressive (AR)* process can be noticed. Combining seasonal (S), *AR* and *MA* observations, a *SARIMA* model could be a suitable for predicting the car density.

Figure 5.20: Autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation analysis.

A grid search was utilized for determining the best model parameters. Four lags were used for the auto regressive component and one for moving average. The integrative part (I) was left at zero since no trend had to be predicted. Two cycles were determined best for the seasonal auto regressive part by the parameter search. With a period of 24 lags/hours, the seasonal offsets of the last two days are considered for the prediction.

In summary, a model of the form $SARIMA(4,0,1) \times (2,0,0)_{24}$ (ref. [81]) was fitted with the car density data from the first 25 days of November 2021.

Figure 5.21a shows the model forecast for the last five days of the month. The predictions for the first half day are quite accurate, after that an increasing error can be observed. Furthermore, the forecasts shows a decaying property over time. Both can be traced back to the model utilizing its own predictions to calculate values even further in the future. A rolling prediction can be used to compensate these effects. Figure 5.21b shows the results for a model only predicting the next hour (one lag) ahead. After each forecast it was refitted with a new ground truth value. This time, no declining amplitude can be observed and the error does not decrease over time. Both models are not able to capture the phase shift between working days and weekend. This can be observed for the forecasts of the morning of November 27. The ramp up in traffic is predicted far earlier as it actually occurs. Training separate models for weekday and weekend could resolve this issue. The *Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)* is lower for the rolling prediction but still fairly high due to the phase error and over-/undershooting.

(a) Full forecast (RMSE: 3.85).

(b) Rolling forecast (RMSE: 2.81).

Figure 5.21: Prediction for the last five days of the time series.

5.3.4 Future Improvements

The time series data gained from detecting vehicles in an image stream was superimposed with the count of parking cars. This number adds fluctuating offset which itself has no expressive power on the subject of traffic density. Moreover, it could lead to misinterpretation, e.g. registering non existing traffic at night. Therefore, methods for excluding such objects should be evaluated in the future. A possible concept could be the use of masks to define areas of interest. Objects detected outside this range are ignored for further processing. Such an approach faces difficulties, for instance cars parking on the street or large vehicles being partially inside and outside the region of interest. A dynamic methods which evaluates whether a vehicle is moving or parking based on observation of subsequent frames during a time interval could be worth considering as well. This would require confidently identifying an object over a long time interval and recursively removing it from the time series once it was classified

as stationary. Furthermore, it must be ensured, that a congestion is not declared as parking after a time threshold was reached.

Anomaly detection could be used to make detections more robust. As seen in Figures 5.16 and 5.17, classes tend to be located in certain areas. Hence detections outside of these regions could be subject for further investigations. Stationary objects, for instance traffic lights should not change their position over time. Exceptions would automatically imply some sort of anomaly which would require some sort of human intervention. The simplest kind would be a classification error, which could be caused by a shift in environmental conditions (e.g. snow, light changes, ...). More severe causes could be a collision with a vehicle (ref. Figure 5.22) or the camera changing its stationary position due to external influence.

Figure 5.22: Traffic light displacement caused by car accident.

In case real time video footage is available, the subject of object tracking could be worth considering. Algorithms such as *Deep Simple Online and Realtime Tracking (SORT)* [82] could be utilized to perform dynamic gradient analysis on passing vehicles. By observing how the center of a moving object moves between frames, it can be determined how fast and in which direction it is moving. Such an analysis can be especially interesting for highways to quickly detect congestion buildup or dynamically regulating the speed limit to ensure safety and improve traffic flow. The direction of movement could also be used for exposing migratory patterns. Such could involve city-country displacement during rush hours in the morning and evening.

Performing traffic density prediction based on previous results from the detection pipeline proved possible but not without error. Better results could be achieved by utilizing deep learning in the forecasting process. *Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs)* such as *Long Short-Term Memorys (LSTMs)* and *Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs)* are proven candidates for such a task. Recently, graph based neuronal networks showed promising results in the field of traffic forecasting [71, 72]. Reliable predictions could be used for anomaly detection and intelligent rerouting.

5.4 Road Side Unit Realization

Performing on site traffic analysis in Amberg, Germany was not possible with the previously described pipeline as no traffic image stream is publicly available yet.

Therefore, the FLIR Flea3 *USB Camera* (ref. Section 2.4) was utilized as a data source for a *Road Side Unit (RSU)* proof-of-concept setup. Figure 5.23 shows the block diagram for an annotation pipeline. The inference service utilizes the software stack proposed in Section 4.3 and is based on the architecture suggested in Section 4.4.1. It transforms images generated by the camera into object lists, which are further processed by a visualization service. The streams of images and detections are merged to a new stream of annotated images in the last step. For evaluation purposes, streaming and visualization are performed on a mobile notebook, while the inference service is hosted on an NVIDIA Jetson AGX Xavier (with *TPU* and *VPU*). Accordingly, data source and sink are on the same device. This has the advantage of directly observing the impact of changes made.

Figure 5.23: Service pipeline for Road Side Unit.

Figure 5.24 shows the *REST* interfaces of the inference service according to *OpenAPI* specification. The endpoint under *Device Information* exposes detailed insight about the platform. The data obtainable can be seen in Listing 4.4 under the *device* node. The *USB Utilities* can be used for binding and unbinding *USB* devices such as hardware accelerators. Under *Model Utilities*, the core functionality of the service can be found. The *model* endpoint returns the names of models available to the service. The model of choice can afterwards be loaded with the *model/load* interface. In addition to the name, the provider is also required. A list of eligible providers can be accessed via the endpoint of the same name. An image can be inferred into an object list via the *inference* interface. The filter values *conf_thres*, *overlap_thres*, *nms_per_class* and *class_filter* can be used to parametrize the detection process. A *Debug* endpoint was implemented to visually evaluate the inference. Here, an annotated image is returned instead of the object list. For streaming application, a web socket interface is used for the interference step to increase throughput while simultaneously decreasing latency.

In Figure 5.25, an output frame of the service pipeline can be seen. It depicts the view from a window of the university on the *Kaiser-Wilhelm-Ring* road running alongside the building. The data was taken and analyzed in real time utilizing the *CUDA* execution provider. The algorithm correctly identified the two people and the car in motion seen in the image. In the upper left corner a frame count is visible. With one image per second, this value was particularly slow when comparing it to the inference benchmark results in Figure 5.2. This drop in performance was caused by the weak wireless connection between the notebook and the Jetson Xavier. A progressive decline in *FPS* was observable with increasing distance to the access point. Such considerations need to be taken into account if developing interconnected wireless

Figure 5.24: OpenAPI interface definitions for YOLOv5 inference service.

AI applications. The pre- and postprocessing impacts the performance as well. The former decodes a compressed image file into an uncompressed numerical tensor which is scaled down to match the input size of the model. Both hardware accelerated image (de-)compression and transformation as well as the choice of the scaling method can significantly improve processing time. The post-processing time is mainly determined by the iterative NMS algorithm. It depends on the number of box candidates which are prefiltered utilizing the parameters *class_filter* and *conf_thres*. Hence, the frame rate is influenced by the inference settings and the number of objects present in the frames. The highest delay is caused by the detection model itself. Naturally, larger models slow down the pipeline as more MAC calculations are performed. Less obvious are the size of the input tensor and the number of classes. Both values influence the size of intermediate tensors which are calculated during inference, therefore determining the number of subsequent calculations in the model graph.

Figure 5.25: YOLOv5 service pipeline evaluating HD real time traffic data in Amberg.

Chapter 6

Summary and Future Work

This work aimed to demonstrate that it is possible to compute AI algorithms efficiently in the field at the edge. This claim could be met, however it was also shown that compromises had to be made. The research area is still very young and fast-moving, which is why there are no best practices that can be relied upon. Both hardware and software require hands on testing to ensure a working application. Furthermore, a lot of background knowledge is necessary to get the maximum performance out of it. In the following, the partial aspects of this work are summarized and it is shown where potentials for future research could lie.

Edge accelerators offer a promising way to realize novel embedded *AI* solutions. However, it can not be denied that the technology is still in its infancy. *GPUs* are the most versatile and performant solution although they leave potential in regards of energy demand. This is where the Google Edge*TPU* shows promising results. It can operate at reasonable inference speed while being highly efficient. This advantage was bought by sacrificing flexibility which in turn makes the process of deployment more difficult. For using the full potential of the coprocessor, *ML* models must be designed to ensure full compatibility with the hardware. Such an approach is only feasible if the focus of *AI* development switches from research to end user deployment. Furthermore, the hardware must be ubiquitous enough to be considered for model design decisions. With Google integrating *TPU* capabilities into their novel Pixel 6 smartphones and *ARM* including a dedicated *Neural Processing Unit (NPU)* [83] in their new *Ethos System on a Chip (SoC)* design, such a scenario could become reality in the near future.

DL models have to be highly optimized for integration into low power applications. Transfer learning proved to be a rewarding method for increasing the accuracy of small object detection models. A future consideration could be a teacher-student approach, where a large model generates training data for a smaller one. The retraining process could be performed on site during periods of low demand. A desirable outcome of this process would be an incremental improvement of the small model accuracy. Adaptive *AI* applications which quickly integrate into new environments could become feasible. Additionally, the work intensive process of manual data labeling could be omitted this way.

Microservices appear to be the preferred solution for embedded intelligence. They have the potential for utilizing the underlying hardware most efficiently and at the same time offering flexibility for highly dynamic applications. Similar to edge accelerators, much development is required before solid end-to-end solutions become feasible. An orchestration framework is required which automatically places *AI* tasks onto edge platforms of heterogeneous edge clusters in an efficient manner. Key figures generated from a benchmarking service could provide a basis for training a scheduling algorithm to handle such a scenario. Reinforcement Learning could be the technology of choice to realize the process of smart task distribution. An intelligent agent would be responsible for ensuring optimal resource utilization in an ever changing environment. Decisions could be improved by generating and evaluating performance metrics during runtime. From a development perspective, the application should be the center of attention opposed to the hardware running it. Similar to modern cloud solutions, software is deployed without considering the underlying infrastructure. Embedded *AI* orchestration should offer similar abstraction by automatically registering hardware accelerators and executing appropriate tasks on them.

An application for smart Microservices was demonstrated by evaluating traffic camera images using a *DL* data pipeline. Object detection models became smaller and more accurate over the years. Therefore, reliably recognizing cars and other traffic participants under reasonable resource consumption. Object detection based image analysis allows for both temporal and spacial investigations for finding possible bottlenecks without designing complex mathematical models of the infrastructure. This insight can be used in urban planning to reshape cities for better traffic flow. Possible improvements could be the utilization of prediction models to capture seasonal behavior and detect anomalies in real time. This could involve detecting or even forecasting congestion at an early state and the rerouting of subsequent vehicles. Such actions would improve user experience and simplify the process of clearing the source of congestion (e.g. car accident). Incorporating the vehicles themselves in the process of data acquisition promises additional potential. The information could be used to characterize the traffic flow of areas which are only sparsely monitored, moreover systems could be more reliable by having support of multiple data sources.

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List of Figures

2.1	NVIDIA inference accelerator platforms.	3
2.2	Raspberry Pi 4 with an Intel Neural Compute Stick 2.	5
2.3	Google Coral Dev Board and Coral USB Accelerator.	5
2.4	FLIR Flea3 USB3 camera with Computar CS mount lens.	6
2.5	Energy Monitoring System v1 with extension modules.	7
2.6	Hardware setup with various edge platforms and accelerators.	8
3.1	Object detection performed on a traffic camera frame from Tampere City.	9
3.2	Using an image classifier as object detector by using a sliding window as input.	10
3.3	Using region proposals with an image classifier to detect objects.	10
3.4	One stage detector: Illustration with 5x5 grid and three anchor boxes.	11
3.5	YOLOv5 output format for one detection.	12
3.6	YOLOv5 image inference before (a) and after (b) thresholding.	12
3.7	<i>Intersection over Union (IoU)</i> formula for two overlapping bounding boxes.	13
3.8	PR-curve family with five classes and an IoU of 0.5.	14
3.9	Converting a mask annotation into a bounding box.	15
3.10	COCO training frame with traffic context.	16
3.11	Cityscape training frame Aachen with fine annotations.	16
3.12	KITTI training frame Karlsruhe.	17
3.13	Citycam training frame camera 164.	17
3.14	Tampere camera frames from two different intersections.	18
3.15	Camera positions in Tampere City with viewing angles.	18
3.16	Visualization frame from dataset labeling policy.	19
3.17	Changing the last layer of an neuronal network to learn new classes.	20
4.1	Splitting a monolithic application into a Microservice structure.	21
4.2	Software stack for AI Microservices.	25
4.3	Class diagram for the core functionality of the YOLOv5 inference service.	26
4.4	Class diagram for the benchmark utility service core.	29
5.1	Service pipeline for performance benchmark.	32
5.2	Average inference time τ_i	33
5.3	EMS measurement block diagram.	33
5.4	KDE plot for platform idle power consumption.	34
5.5	Normalized inference power KDE plot.	35

5.6	Energy required to perform one inference for each provider.	35
5.7	Model profiles for a potential scheduling scheme.	36
5.8	Service pipeline for accuracy evaluation.	37
5.9	Label instances for each dataset.	38
5.10	Transfer Learning pipeline for YOLOv5n model.	38
5.11	Traffic light detections for COCO6 model (blue) and missed instances (red).	40
5.12	Car density for Lapintie (Pohjoiseen) during November 2021.	42
5.13	Car density for Rautatienkatu (Etelaan) during November 2021.	43
5.14	Car count occurrence heat maps November 2021.	43
5.15	Rautatienkatu (Etelaan) intersection November 21th at 15:56pm.	44
5.16	Car traffic flow overlays for November 2021.	44
5.17	Person traffic flow overlays for November 2021.	45
5.18	Service pipeline for predicting future traffic density.	45
5.19	Car density for Lapintie (Pohjoiseen) during November 2021.	46
5.20	Autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation analysis.	46
5.21	Prediction for the last five days of the time series.	47
5.22	Traffic light displacement caused by car accident.	48
5.23	Service pipeline for Road Side Unit.	49
5.24	OpenAPI interface definitions for YOLOv5 inference service.	50
5.25	YOLOv5 service pipeline evaluating HD real time traffic data in Amberg.	50

List of Tables

2.1	NVIDIA Jetson hardware specifications.	4
3.1	Traffic dataset comparison.	15
5.1	YOLOv5n load and warmup timings in seconds for different providers.	32
5.2	Mean power offset for different providers in Watt.	35
5.3	COCO mAP_{50} score for Tampere validation dataset.	39

List of Listings

- 4.1 Example REST endpoint. 23
- 4.2 Example JSON response. 23
- 4.3 Shortened inference service response. 26
- 4.4 Shortened benchmark dump for idle scenario. 30
- 6.1 Quantization log for YOLOv5n model. 64

Appendix

```

1 | Edge TPU Compiler version 16.0.384591198
2 | Input: yolov5n-int8.tflite
3 | Output: yolov5n-int8_edgetpu.tflite
4 |
5 | Operator                Count    Status
6 |
7 | SUB                     3        More than one subgraph is not supported
8 | MUL                     57       Mapped to Edge TPU
9 | MUL                     21       More than one subgraph is not supported
10 | LOGISTIC                60       Mapped to Edge TPU
11 | TRANSPOSE               3        Operation is otherwise supported,
12 |                          but not mapped due to some unspecified limitation
13 | STRIDED_SLICE           9        More than one subgraph is not supported
14 | RESHAPE                  3        Operation is otherwise supported,
15 |                          but not mapped due to some unspecified limitation
16 | RESHAPE                  1        More than one subgraph is not supported
17 | RESHAPE                  2        Mapped to Edge TPU
18 | CONCATENATION           3        More than one subgraph is not supported
19 | CONCATENATION           1        Operation is otherwise supported,
20 |                          but not mapped due to some unspecified limitation
21 | CONCATENATION           13       Mapped to Edge TPU
22 | RESIZE_NEAREST_NEIGHBOR 2        Mapped to Edge TPU
23 | DEQUANTIZE               1        Operation is working on an unsupported data type
24 | CONV_2D                  60       Mapped to Edge TPU
25 | QUANTIZE                 9        More than one subgraph is not supported
26 | QUANTIZE                 3        Operation is otherwise supported,
27 |                          but not mapped due to some unspecified limitation
28 | QUANTIZE                 13       Mapped to Edge TPU
29 | MAX_POOL_2D              3        Mapped to Edge TPU
30 | ADD                      7        Mapped to Edge TPU
31 | ADD                      3        More than one subgraph is not supported
32 | PAD                      7        Mapped to Edge TPU

```

Listing 6.1: Quantization log for YOLOv5n model.

NVIDIA Jetson AGX Xavier - Benchmark

Device Information

Supported Provider						
ONNX RT True 1.9.1	CPU True N/A	OpenVino True 2021.4.1	CUDA True 10.2.300/8.2.1	TensorRT True 8.0.1	TFLite True 2.5.0.post1	EdgeTPU True 16.0

Carrier Platform							
	Name	CPU	RAM	AI-Chip	AI-Chip-Interface	On-Chip-Memory	AI-Chip-OPs
	NVIDIA Jetson AGX Xavier	8-core NVIDIA Carmel ArmA@v8.2 64-bit	32 GB LPDDR4x	512 core Volta GPU with 64 Tensor Cores	PCIe	Shared with CPU	32 TOPs

Auxiliary Accelerators					
	Name	AI-Chip	AI-Chip-Interface	On-Chip-Memory	AI-Chip-OPs
	Coral Accelerator	Google EdgeTPU	USB 3.0	8 MB	4 TOPs
	Name	AI-Chip	AI-Chip-Interface	On-Chip-Memory	AI-Chip-OPs
	Intel NCS2	Intel Movidius Myriad X VPU with 16 SHAVE cores	USB 3.0	512 MB LPDDR4 + 2.5 MB Centralized	1 TOPs

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NVIDIA Jetson AGX Xavier - Benchmark

Yolov5n

Model Properties

Model Profiles

Model Measurements

Metric	Phase	CPU	OpenVino	TF-Lite	CUDA	TRT
$\bar{\theta}(\text{Time})$ [s]	Load	0.153	2.970	0.009	3.764	189.948
$\bar{\theta}(\text{Time})$ [s]	Warmup	0.280	0.281	0.174	2.949	0.053
$\bar{\theta}(\text{Time})$ [s]	Inference	0.259	0.241	0.136	0.047	0.023
$\bar{\theta}(\text{Power})$ [W]	Idle	8.315	8.329	8.336	8.314	8.314
$\bar{\theta}(\text{Power})$ [W]	Load	9.223	9.821	8.891	9.945	10.827
$\bar{\theta}(\text{Power})$ [W]	Warmup	10.095	10.200	9.238	10.426	10.786
$\bar{\theta}(\text{Power})$ [W]	Inference	9.181	9.044	9.114	14.233	16.217
$\bar{\theta}(\text{Energy}) / \text{Execution}$ [mWh]	Load	0.392	8.103	0.021	10.398	571.001
$\bar{\theta}(\text{Energy}) / \text{Execution}$ [mWh]	Warmup	0.786	0.797	0.448	8.540	0.158
$\bar{\theta}(\text{Energy}) / \text{Execution}$ [mWh]	Inference	0.661	0.605	0.344	0.185	0.103
$\Delta(\bar{\theta}(\text{Energy})) / \text{Execution}$ [mWh]	Load	0.039	1.243	0.001	1.705	132.323
$\Delta(\bar{\theta}(\text{Energy})) / \text{Execution}$ [mWh]	Warmup	0.139	0.147	0.045	1.729	0.035
$\Delta(\bar{\theta}(\text{Energy})) / \text{Execution}$ [mWh]	Inference	0.062	0.049	0.030	0.077	0.050

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